

ISic1441

I.Sicily inscription 1441

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

conglomerate

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Εύμαί

2. δαϛ

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285089

EDR 120812

EDCS 41300041

PHI 175652

Bibliography

Dubois, L. 1989. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile : contribution à l'étude du vocabulaire grec colonial. Rome. At 42 (<http://www.persee.fr/doc/>

efr_0000-0000_1989_cat_119_1)

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 57

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1970. Epigrafia selinuntina. *Kokalos*. 16: 268-294. At 286 no.9

Grotta, C. 2010. Zeus Meilichios a Selinunte. Rome. At 103-104 no.2 tav.25b

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